

Microservice Name	ftgo-microservice	VAE-C
ftgo-order-service	<p> CreateOrderRequest, CreateOrderResponse, DeliveryInformation, GetOrderResponse, GetRestaurantResponse, InvalidMenuItemException, LineItemQuantityChange, MenuItem, MenuItemIdAndQuantity, OptimisticOfflineLockException, Order, OrderController, OrderControllerTest, OrderDetails, OrderDetailsMother, OrderLineItem, OrderLineItems, OrderMinimumNotMetException, OrderNotFoundException, OrderRepository, OrderRevision, OrderService, OrderServiceConfiguration, OrderServiceWithRepositoriesConfiguration, OrderState, OrderWebConfiguration, PaymentInformation, Restaurant, RestaurantController, RestaurantMother, RestaurantNotFoundException, RestaurantRepository, ReviseOrderRequest, RevisedOrder </p>	<p> Action, ConsumerNotFoundException, CourierAvailability, CourierRepository, CreateOrderRequest, CreateOrderResponse, CreateRestaurantResponse, GetRestaurantResponse, LineItemQuantityChange, MenuItemIdAndQuantity, OptimisticOfflineLockException, Order, OrderController, OrderControllerTest, OrderDetails, OrderDetailsMother, OrderMinimumNotMetException, OrderNotFoundException, OrderRepository, OrderRevision, OrderState, PaymentInformation, RestaurantServiceDomainConfiguration, ReviseOrderRequest, RevisedOrder </p>
ftgo-restaurant-service	<p> CreateRestaurantRequest, CreateRestaurantResponse, GetRestaurantResponse, MenuItem, Restaurant, RestaurantController, RestaurantMenu, RestaurantRepository, RestaurantService, RestaurantServiceDomainConfiguration </p>	<p> ConsumerController, ConsumerServiceConfiguration, CreateRestaurantRequest, CreateRestaurantResponse, MenuItem, MenuItemIdAndQuantity, OrderDetails, OrderDetailsMother, OrderLineItem, PaymentInformation, Restaurant, RestaurantController, RestaurantMenu, RestaurantMother, RestaurantRepository, RestaurantService, RestaurantServiceDomainConfiguration, RevisedOrder </p>
ftgo-consumer-service	<p> Consumer, ConsumerController, ConsumerNotFoundException, ConsumerRepository, ConsumerService, ConsumerServiceConfiguration, ConsumerVerificationFailedException, ConsumerWebConfiguration, CreateConsumerRequest, CreateConsumerResponse, GetConsumerResponse </p>	<p> Action, ConsumerNotFoundException, ConsumerServiceConfiguration, ConsumerVerificationFailedException, ConsumerWebConfiguration, Courier, CourierAvailability, CourierRepository, CreateConsumerRequest, CreateConsumerResponse, CreateRestaurantResponse, DeliveryInformation, GetConsumerResponse, GetOrderResponse, GetRestaurantResponse, InvalidMenuItemException, LineItemQuantityChange, MenuItemIdAndQuantity, OptimisticOfflineLockException, Order, OrderController, OrderDetails, OrderDetailsMother, OrderLineItems, OrderMinimumNotMetException, OrderServiceWithRepositoriesConfiguration, PaymentInformation, RestaurantNotFoundException, RestaurantServiceDomainConfiguration, ReviseOrderRequest, RevisedOrder </p>
ftgo-kitchen-service	<p> GetRestaurantResponse, MenuItem, Restaurant, RestaurantController, RestaurantMenu, RestaurantRepository </p>	<p> Action, ConsumerNotFoundException, ConsumerServiceConfiguration, ConsumerVerificationFailedException, CourierRepository, CreateRestaurantResponse, GetRestaurantResponse, InvalidMenuItemException, MenuItemIdAndQuantity, OrderDetails, OrderDetailsMother, OrderLineItem, OrderLineItems, OrderServiceConfiguration, OrderServiceWithRepositoriesConfiguration, OrderWebConfiguration, PaymentInformation, Plan, Restaurant, RestaurantController, RestaurantMenu, RestaurantRepository, RestaurantService, RestaurantServiceDomainConfiguration, RevisedOrder </p>
ftgo-delivery-service	<p> Action, Courier, CourierAvailability, CourierRepository, Plan, Restaurant, RestaurantRepository </p>	<p> Consumer, ConsumerController, ConsumerRepository, ConsumerService, MenuItemIdAndQuantity, OrderController, OrderDetailsMother, OrderService, Restaurant, RestaurantController </p>